

METHODS OF DETERMINING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL CAPACITY, TENDENCIES, INTEREST AND ABILITIES

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Abstract: Methodological and practical recommendations are given in this article to determine professional abilities, inclinations and abilities to interest schoolchildren in the profession. Also, opinions on training students for professions were discussed.

Key words: Educational system, profession, skill, competence, methodology, ability, technology, professional inclination.

It is known that our nation has been paying special attention to the education of the young generation, especially to preparing young people for work and teaching them trades. We can also see this in our proverbs, such as 10 from a trade, and 40 trades for a young man. After our country gained independence, attention to this field increased. A new type of education, including labor education at school, and the establishment of vocational education institutions based on it, to direct students to professions and prepare them to continue studying in colleges, is being accelerated. The upbringing of them as a free-thinking, well-rounded person who is a master of his work is included among the priority tasks of our society, because it is such young people who can build the great future of our country.

Today, every person's desire to find his place in the world of professions, to realize his professional identity, to find his place in society, and his interest in it is increasing day by day. Choosing which one among thousands of professions, knowing whether a person's inclinations, abilities and interests are compatible with it or not, is of great importance in a person's perspective. In this regard, children are given a lot of information about the professions of interest to them in preschool educational institutions, the first understanding of the world of professions, basic labor skills through games.

Vocational guidance in general secondary schools is provided continuously to students in grades 1-9, based on psychological-pedagogical diagnosis of the individual. This process is carried out by teachers of vocational education, experts, psychologists, teachers of basic subjects and class leaders. Vocational orientation and psychological-pedagogical regional diagnostic centers coordinate and methodically guide these works. Vocational guidance commissions, which are

established annually and are headed by the school director, operate in every general secondary school. The commissions give recommendations to the graduates for the training courses of the selected academic lyceums and vocational colleges based on the final conclusions. Some elements of vocational guidance are provided in secondary specialized, vocational education analysis and higher education institutions, in the divisions of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population, in the Ministry of Defense and in post-secondary educational institutions. and continuing studies of school graduates in academic lyceums, KHK and higher education institutions, career selection work in enterprises will continue to be deepened and expanded.

A comprehensive system of vocational guidance is gradually being formed in the country. This unified system currently includes schools, academic lyceums, vocational colleges, vocational guidance centers, youth social movements, higher education institutions, relevant state structures of the employment service, enterprises and institutions regardless of the form of ownership. Bilateral and multilateral cooperation activities in structural structures and between them are gradually being organized on the basis of existing regulatory and legal documents - work on guiding students to professions. In this regard, provision of the mentioned educational institutions, enterprises and organizations with appropriate personnel will be formed by increasing the training of psychologists, professional counselors, psychophysicologists, sociologists, etc.

Taking this into account, attention should be paid to the teaching methodology of the course "Students' career orientation" in the curricula of the labor education and vocational teachers being prepared in pedagogical institutes and universities. big In order for students to consciously choose their future profession, to have full information and information about their chosen profession, enough materials were included in the "basics of production" course in the first half of the 8-9th grades, and they were studied in full. It is envisaged to create special opportunities for development.

Thus, the knowledge and skills acquired by the students in the field of labor education in the 5th-7th grades, the information they learned about the professions based on the general education subjects, and the lessons and mass activities in the school and extracurricular systems. the information they receive about professions in training - leads them to consciously choose a specific profession.

Taking this into account, in the 9th grade, it is planned to carry out career selection activities carried out in the school system, and in the 9th grade, organizational-mass and cooperation activities specific to the choice of a profession will be carried out. The following lesson plans have been developed based on them. Since the topics are covered in the thesis, they are directed to the comprehensive study of additional materials, schemes and other information. Fill in, enrich, deepen and expand pedagogical-psychological and methodical materials specific to choosing a profession using additional sources. From additional materials, often focus on regional, local and best practices information. Broadly describe the activities of regional academic lyceums and vocational colleges related to the topic, educational work, and career-oriented materials. Pay special attention to students learning these topics independently. Focus more on putting the material students are learning into a system or model.

Failure to take into account students' professional abilities, inclinations, interests and abilities can lead to the following shortcomings: Failure to take into account the teacher's abilities when choosing a profession. From the teacher's choice of profession, the health, ability, and other factors of his interest in a specific profession are not comprehensively studied. It seems that they are forcibly involved in the organization and conduct of cultural and moral activities to participate in meaningful educational activities. As a result of such a natural situation, activity, initiative and creativity are lost in both people (teacher and student). The teacher's lack of clear and creative planning of the educational work of guiding students to the profession.

This reason is the result of the homogeneity of the demand for the education of the single curriculum of labor education and the neglect of the spirituality of the profession in the father-profession and mentor-apprentice systems. As a result, the teacher does not pay special attention to the educational side of his education, relying on the masterpieces of our spiritual heritage, rich in didactic literature, religious sources, local history materials, the possibilities of spiritual formation of the student's choice of work and profession based on the plan and program. The teacher should not rely on the program or the textbook, and should not work on the profession chosen by the students based on their interests and capabilities, based on the requirements of the father - profession and the teacher - student. The refusal to choose a desired profession that cannot capture the attention, heart, mind and activity of the student will have a negative effect on the distance from the creative study of the works and activities of skilled masters and specialists who cannot satisfy their spiritual needs.

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